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Areas Cultivated with Organic Agriculture in Europe

Between 2010 and 2020 they grew by an average of 158%

Eurostat calculates the areas cultivated with organic agriculture in Europe. The definition of area cultivated with organic farming derives from the European Union regulation which has identified ways to define and control the labelling, processing and marketing of EU organic products. The value is expressed as a percentage of the total cultivated area by country.

Ranking of countries by value of cultivated area with organic agriculture in Europe in 2020. Austria ranks first in value of cultivated area with organic agriculture with an amount of 25.7%, followed by Estonia with an amount of 22.4%, and from Sweden with an amount of 20.3%. In the middle of the ranking are Spain, Greece, and France with an amount of area cultivated with organic farming equal to 9.98%, 9.59% and 8.71% respectively. Bulgaria closes the ranking with an amount of 2.3%, followed by Ireland with an amount of 1.66% and Malta with an amount of 0.62%. On average in 2020, 9.73% of the cultivated areas in the countries considered was dedicated to organic farming.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage change of the areas cultivated with organic agriculture between 2010 and 2020. Bulgaria ranks first in the value of the percentage change of the areas cultivated with organic agriculture between 2010 and 2020 with an amount of 460% equal to an amount of 1.8 units, followed by Malta with a value equal to 310% equal to an amount of 0.42 units and by France with a value equal to 300% equal to an amount of 5.81 units. In the middle of the table are Germany with an amount of 163% equal to an amount of 3.69%, followed by Latvia with a value of 161% equal to 5.59 units and Slovenia with an amount of 161% equal to 3.89 units. The Czech Republic closes the ranking with an amount of 124% equal to an amount of 2.93 units, followed by Greece with an amount of 121% equal to an amount of 1.75 units and by Poland with an amount of 107% equal to a value of 0.22 units. On average between 2010 and 2020, the average value of the percentage change for the countries considered went from a value of 6.2 to 9.77 with a change of 3.57 points or 158%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Five clusters are identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Latvia, Italy, Czech Republic, Finland;
- Cluster 2: Cyprus, Luxembourg, Poland, France, Hungary, Belgium, the Netherlands;
- Cluster 3: Austria, Sweden, Estonia;
- Cluster 4: Spain, Denmark, Greece, Slovenia, Lithuania, Germany, Slovakia, Portugal;
- Cluster 5: Ireland, Malta, Bulgaria, Romania.

From the point of view of the median, it is possible to identify the following ordering of the clusters, namely $C3=22.41 > C1=15.06 > C4=10.07 > C2=4.63 > C5=1.98$. From a geographical point of view it is possible to notice a great heterogeneity of the countries. That is, there are no real areas per cluster. Countries even distant from each other participate in the same clusters and neighboring countries do

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not necessarily participate in the same cluster, with some exceptions, namely: Spain and Portugal; France, Belgium and the Netherlands; Bulgaria and Romania.

Network Analysis with Euclidean distance. A network analysis with Euclidean distance is analyzed below. Three complex clusters and one simplified cluster are therefore identified. Specifically, there are the following connections:

- The Netherlands has a connection with Luxembourg for a value of 0.26 and with Hungary for a value of 0.25;
- Hungary has a connection with the Netherlands worth 0.25 and with Luxembourg worth 0.32;
- Luxembourg has a connection with the Netherlands worth 0.26 units, with Hungary worth 0.32 units and with Cyprus worth 0.25 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Luxembourg in the amount of 0.25 units.

There is also the following complex network structure:

- Germany has a connection with Lithuania in the amount of 0.29 units and with Portugal in the amount of 0.22 units;
- Portugal has a connection with Germany in the amount of 0.22 units and with Lithuania in the amount of 0.34 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Germany amounting to 0.29 units and with Portugal amounting to 0.34 units.

There is a complex network structure that is:

- Bulgaria has a connection with Ireland in the amount of 0.32 units;
- Ireland has a connection with Romania in the amount of 0.3 units, and with Bulgaria in the amount of 0.32 units;
- Romania has a connection with Ireland for the amount of 0.3 units.

There are also the following simplified network structures, namely:

- Belgium and France have a connection equal to an amount of 0.34 units;
- Spain and Slovenia have a connection amounting to 0.34 units.

Conclusions. The areas cultivated with organic agriculture in Europe increased on average by 158% between 2010 and 2020. European countries on average employ 9.73% of the arable areas in organic cultivation. The sensitivity towards organic farming of Europeans is due on the one hand to the need to increase the agricultural offer and on the other hand to the issues connected to the applications of the green economy in agriculture. In fact, organic farming in general also involves the recognition of brands protected by production regulations, such as for example the various DOP and IGP, which have the possibility of guaranteeing a high level of quality and typicality of the products. A type of agriculture that is also able to respect the historical-cultural dimension of rural areas with the possibility of increasing sustainability and reducing pollution. There are also significant benefits in terms of consumer health with relevant positive effects also in terms of public health.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

C3>C1>C4>C2>C5

- C1
- C2
- C3
- C4
- C5

